

THE ROLE OF KOMIL SINDAROV NOT ONLY IN JURISPRUDENCE
BUT ALSO IN LITERATURE

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Abstract:

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About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Every reader thinks of characters like Hercule Poirot and Sherlock Holmes when they think of a detective. In Uzbek literature, the detective works of writers such as Ulmas Umarbekov and Tahir Malik are well known and popular among readers as well. It is also clear to many of us that writers of the new era literature, such as Azamat Korjovov and Isakjon Nishonov, wrote about this genre. Among these writers, there is another great writer who may not be known by many people. This writer is Komil Sindarov. This person studied law for many years and wrote down the situations that he witnessed. Komiljon Sindarov, known as the famous Uzbek detective novelist of the 21st century, was born in the village of Kurgan, located between Oktov and Karatov, in Koshrobot district of the Samarkand region.

Although, the name Motherland is not a village, and its name is not even shown on the map, it is no secret that the name of this village is written in large golden letters in the history of Uzbek folk art and culture. In fact, one of the five epic schools in our country is connected with this place of Bakhshis - the village of Kurgan. Kamil Sindarov was born and grew up in this village, as well as many famous representatives of literature. Komiljon was the fourth of ten children, to study well, his parents sent him to the famous 56th secondary school which located five kilometers away in the village of Josh. Komiljon's mother, Amirov Haji, worked as the headmistress of the village library.

This thing made a lot of sense to Kamiljon, that's why familiarity and love for the book started from this period. "My mother read the books until I was literate, but later I couldn't get my head off the books. By the time I finished high school, I

had managed to read almost all the books in this library"⁵⁹said the poet. From a young age, he read with interest the poems of Gafur Ghulam, Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov, Normurod Narzullaev, their simple but beautiful and charming verses and philosophical thoughts captivated him. Later, he enjoyed the poems of such artists as Muhammad Yusuf, Sirojiddin Sayyid, Mahmud Toir, Iqbal Mirza, Sadulla Hakim, O'tkir Rahmat, Farida Afroz, Abduvali Qutfiddin, Zulfiya Muminova, Hosiyat Bobomurodova. "Even now, their books don't leave my desk"⁶⁰says the poet. In 1978, he graduated from school with a "Gold Medal" due to his eagerness to learn. Then he entered the Samarkand State University and began to study at the Faculty of Law. During his almost forty years of work, he has been working as both a practitioner and a theoretician, contributing to reforms in the field of judicial law. Kamil Sindarov currently holds the scientific degree "Doctor of Legal Sciences".

Komil Sindarov used to practice poetry when he was still in school, but he considered it just a hobby. But gradually, this "hobby" began to turn into "love" for the young artist. Because creativity in the field of literature was in the blood of Kamil Sindarov's ancestors. Therefore, his father Sindor Baba and the son of Ergash Jumanbulbul were cousins. Kamil Sindarov wrote many poems. "Qalbim javohiri" (2006), "Vasling qumsab" (2007), "Sog`insam Onajonim" (2007), "Oqqan daryo oqar ekan" (2008), "O`zing mening yagonamsan" (2008), "Toshkenti Azim Derlar" (2009), "Ayol borki" (2010), "Ilinj" (2011), "Shukronalik shukuhi (2012), "Bir kam dunyo... korkam dunyo" (2014), "Qalbim Sadosi" (2016) and other poetry books saw the face of the world.

It should be said that most of Komil Sindarov's poems are about love, and many fans are troubled by only one question. "To whom are your love poems dedicated?" The poet answers this question as follows: "I appreciate and love life, the motherland where I was born and raised - my Motherland, kindness, goodness, kind-minded people, beauty, sophistication, mother nature, my profession, my family, my parents, my wife, my children, my brothers and my friends. I wish them good and only good. And on the contrary, if I see people who spend their lives in vain, indifferent, oppressed, my anger boils. This is the source of the fire of love and hatred in my heart"⁶¹. As a result, Komil Sindarov was admitted to the Union of Writers of Uzbekistan.

Komil Sindarov, who plunged into the source of creative research, started the detective genre of literary prose. Komiljon Sindarov remembers his love for prose through strange incident: "At that time, the national writer of Uzbekistan, teacher Khudoyberdi Tokhtaboev, whose works have been translated into many languages

⁵⁹ Qalbim qo`shig`i (I jild)- TOSHKENT 2010

⁶⁰ Qalbim qo`shig`i (I jild)- TOSHKENT 2010

⁶¹ Komil Sindarov .So`z -O`zbekiston xalq yozuvchisi Muhammad Ali

of the world, read my book of poetry called "The Song of My Heart" and invited me to his presence through the publishing house. Although in my youth I enjoyed reading the works of the teacher, I did not know him personally. We met:

- Your poems were very pleasing to me, your bride Sanobarkhan, - said the teacher, taking my book in hand, - written in a simple, popular, educated language. But...

The teacher took a break and sipped the tea from the cup. My heart was pulled back. "It must be raining now!" I thought about that and sank into the chair.

- But... the lyrics you wrote for "Kalbim Zhosighi" made a great impression on me, - the writer continued in a sincere tone. - You have poured everything in your heart. It turned out very beautiful. You have a talent for writing. Why not try one yourself?

I was thinking. At first "are they kidding?" I thought. But seeing the seriousness on the face of my interlocutor, I realized that I had come to the wrong conclusion.

- Today's Uzbek literature lacks the detective genre. You are a lawyer. You worked in the prosecutor's office, court offices. You know the secrets of the industry that are not known to writers. It will come in handy. It's natural for your works to come out live.

"Master, I'm sorry... I'm over fifty," I said, not knowing what to say. - To start writing at this age...

- Really? You are still a young boy!" said the teacher with a smile. - If you count one a year, you can write at least thirty detective novels before you reach my age!

That night, I leafed through my memory book and began to write down what I saw and experienced in artistic paints. ⁶²

Then he continued his creative research, tried the detective genre of prose and wrote the first short story "A costly mistake". The book was quickly reprinted. Then in a row "The Secret of the Timurid Library", "Delayed Revenge". His stories, built on interesting plots, such as "In the footsteps of the golden throne of the Emirates", "Night murder", "Stolen childhood", "Murder in the pharmacy" have reached the hands of readers. Kamil Sindarov knows what kind of book a reader needs today and has been creating interesting works based on that.

In conclusion, Komil Sindarov, a lawyer who has been working in the field of law for many years, a scientist who has done many scientific works, a grandfather who brought up world and Asian chess champions - grandmasters like Javohir and Islambek, Khumayun, a prolific literature lover who publishes seven volumes of his

⁶² Qalbim qo`shig`i (I jild)- TOSHKENT 2010

works - how many As the youngest representative of the century-old Kurgan school of epics, we are all happy that he continues his research.

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